

Comparison Of Obesity And Its Associated Factors Between Private Versus Government School Sector School Going Adolescents Of District Muzaffarabad Azad Kashmir

Zarnab Munir, Munazza Nazir, Mudasar Hafiz, Rubina Rafique, Nouman Kareem Qurashi, Naheem Ahmed

Article Info	Abstract
<p><i>Article History</i></p> <p>Received: April 06, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 08, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Private, Government, Schools, Adolescents</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5669224</p>	<p><i>Background</i></p> <p><i>Obesity, one of the major dilemmas of the world, with changing lifestyles it is associated with many cardiovascular, cerebrovascular risks, metabolic and psychosocial disorders. Currently the prevalence of obesity is rising worldwide also in young children and adolescents. Around 1 billion populations all over the world are estimated to be obese till 2030.</i></p> <p><i>Objective: To determine the frequency of obesity and overweight and to identify the frequency of factors causing obesity in school going adolescents of District Muzaffarabad Azad Kashmir.</i></p> <p><i>Material & Methods</i></p> <p><i>Study Design: Cross sectional Setting: Government & Private schools in Muzaffarabad. Data collection: A total of 288 adolescents were included in this study who presented with age 16-20 years of grade 9th and 10th were identified by name from ministry of Education and then the schools were stratified by ownership into government and private schools. The demographic details was noted. Data was entered and analyzed in SPSS 25.</i></p> <p><i>Results: In this study, total 288 students were included. There were 151(52.4%) male and 137(47.6%) female. The mean age was 15.6+1.02 years. Among 288 adolescents, 152 adolescents with normal weight, 88 students belong to government and 69 were belong to private school. 113 were overweight, 54 were belong to government and 59 were belong to private school. 23 students were obese, out of 23, only 3 was belong to government and 20 were belong to private school. P value less than 0.05 was significant</i></p> <p><i>Conclusion: Adolescents living in Pakistan are at larger risk for obesity & overweight. There's a need to establish a national program for the prevention & treatment of obesity and its related factors.</i></p>

Introduction

Obesity among children and adolescents is a public health problem around the worldwide. Over the last two decades, the prevalence of overweight & obese children in general population has doubled in both developed or developing countries. (1) More over 1.9 billion adult's person aged 18 & older are overweight, according to WHO estimates, with over 650 million adults being obese. (2) Between 2011 and 2014, 36.5 percent of adults in the United States were obese. (3) It's observed that 30.0% of obesity starts in childhood & out of that 50 to 80% become obese in adults. (4) In adults, obesity is hard to treat and childhood obesity has long-term negative effects, prevention of adult's obesity has become a public health priority

In 2015 study, Overweight or obesity was found in 27.87% of students (government schools 10.49%, private schools 45.1%). (5) A study was conducted among adolescent's school going girls, 9 to 16 years studying in many schools in rural area of Kavre area, Nepal found that whole frequency of stunning, underweight and thinness was 21.07, 31.88% and 14.84%. (6)

Pakistan is one of the countries where the double burden of overweight or obesity & thinness or stunting is increasing. According to one study from 57.0 low and middle income countries of adolescents, all burden of under-nutrition and over-nutrition has been described in Pakistan. However, as compared to obesity or overweight, the frequency of malnutrition resulting to stunting and thinness is particularly high in Pakistani girls. (7) The rationale of the study to find the frequency of obesity & overweight or also identify the frequency of factors causing obesity in school going adolescents of District Muzaffarabad Azad Kashmir.

Methodology:

This cross sectional study was conducted from Jan 2018 to June 2018 of in District Private and Government school Muzaffarabad Lahore. A total of 288 sample size was calculated with 80% power of test and 5% level of significance by taking expecting 50% of obesity/overweight in adolescents

All adolescents presented with age 16-20 years of grade 9th and 10th were included from the study and also identified by name from ministry of Education and then the schools were stratified by ownership into government and private schools. From each stratum schools were selected by simple random sampling. Demographic data was also noted. A predesigned proforma was used to find the frequency of obesity and overweight in adolescent.

Data was entered in SPSS 25. Age, weight, Height and BMI were presented as mean and standard deviation. Categorical data like Gender, Central Obesity, Family history were presented as frequency and percentages. Chi square test was applied to compare the obesity or overweight between government and private schools

Results:

In this study, total 288 respondents were included. There were 151(52.4%) male and 137(47.6%) female. The mean age was 15.6±1.02 years. 279(96.9%) students were lie between the age group 14 to 17 years and only 9(3.1%) students above 17 years Table: 1 The mean height, weight, BMI and waist in government & private school as shown in Table: 2

Out of 288 sample, 144 students belong to Government school and 144 for private school. It was observed that 140(48.6%) students for grade 9 and 148(51.4%) students for grade 10. Regarding the nutritional status of the adolescents, among 288 adolescents almost 52(52.8%) had normal weight. Similarly, 113(39.2%) overweight and obesity that is 23(8.0%). Table:3

152 adolescents with normal weight, 88 students belong to government and 69 were belong to private school. 113 were overweight, 54 were belong to government and 59 were belong to private school. 23 students were obese, out of 23, only 3 was belong to government and 20 were belong to private school. P value less than 0.05 was significant. Table: 4

The result about frequency of intake of junk food items showed that more than half 131(45.5) took junk food daily, 90(31.3%) took once a week and 34(11.8%) took 2-3 times per month. Nearly more than half of the students 126(43.8%) took fruit daily, 118(41%) took fruit once a week and only 11(3.8%) took fruit 2-3 times per month. Frequency of fruit consumption daily, once a week and 2-3 times per month as shown in table: There were no significant relationship between government and private school with junk food taken or fruit consumption. Table: 5

55(19.1%) students daily participate in sports, 149(51.7%) students weekly participate in sports and 84(29.2%) participate in sports monthly. Stratification of government and private school students role in taken junk food and fruit had shown in table: there was significant relationship between government and private school with sports habits and screen time. P value less than 0.05 was significant.

Table:1 Gender and Age distribution

Gender	Male	Frequency (%)
	Female	151(52.4%)
Age	Mean+ SD	15.6±1.02
	14-17 years	279(96.9%)
	Above 17	9(3.1%)

Table: 2 Comparison of mean in height, weight, BMI and Waist

	Government School	Private School	P value
Height	159.3±5.4	163.15±9.16	0.001
Weight	51.10±8.2	60.11±13.64	0.045
BMI	20.08±2.87	22.89±5.68	0.006
Waist	69.82±6.9	77.44±10.42	0.023

Table: 3 Frequency of Nutritional Status

	Frequency(%)
Normal	152(52.8%)
Overweight	113(39.2%)
Obese	23(8.0%)

Table: 4 Frequency Distribution of Nutritional Status

	Government school	Private School	P value
Normal	83(54.6%)	69(45.4%)	0.01
Overweight	54(47.8%)	59(52.2%)	
Obese	3(13%)	20(87%)	

Table: 5 Frequency of junk food and fruit consumption

	Daily	Once a week	2-3 times month	P value
Junk Food	131(45.5%)	90(31.3%)	34(11.8%)	0.34
Fruit consumption	126(43.8%)	118(41%)	11(3.8%)	0.45

Discussion:

Obesity and overweight are extra fat accumulations in the body that have been connected to major diet-related non-communicable diseases that have an adverse effects on human health.(8) Obesity & overweight are the 5th largest causes of death worldwide, and they have a crucial role in the world's leading killer diseases, such as heart disease, diabetes and several malignancies.(9)

Obesity, one of the major dilemmas of the world, with changing lifestyles it is associated with many cardiovascular, cerebrovascular risks, metabolic and psychosocial disorders. Currently the prevalence of obesity is rising worldwide also in young children and adolescents. Around 1 billion populations all over the world are estimated to be obese till 2030. In Pakistan the situation is in transition with coexistent under nutrition and over nutrition. (10)

In 2018 study, the prevalence of obesity & overweight was 5.21% % 4.7%.(11) Yetubie et al.(12)In Ambo town, 4.39% of adolescents were overweight. It was also reported from Mekele city (2.40%), (13) and rural Wardha, India (2.1%).(14) Though, it's lower than those reported from Addis Ababa (8.51%). (15)

According to Jagadesan, *et al.*(16)reported a larger prevalence of obesity or overweight in private compared to government schools. As compared to our study, there were also high prevalence of obesity and overweight with private and government school. The high incidence of overweight or obese adolescents at private schools may be due to socioeconomic level and lifestyle factors such as physical activity decrease, higher intake of junk foods, and bus transportation to school.

The prevalence of underweight was found to be 39.9% which is almost comparable with the study done in Ambo which was 27.5%, 16 and 24.4% done in Chiro.(17) The frequency of overweight or obesity was 27.7% (private schools 45.19%, government schools–10.49%). As compare to our study, the prevalence of obesity 3(2.1%) in government and 20(13.5%) in private school, and overweight in 54(38.6%) in private and 59(39.9%) in government school. The height, weight, BMI, waist circumference, waist-hip ratio was highly significant among private school adolescents than government school adolescents.(5) As compared to our study, the mean weight, height, BMI and waist also highly significant among private than government school.

Conclusion:

The prevalence of obesity (8.0%) and overweight (39.2%) among adolescent in Kashmir districts. Adolescents living in Pakistan are at high risk for obesity & overweight. There's a need to establish a national program for the prevention & treatment of obesity and its related factors.

References

- Zakharova I, Klimov L, Kuryaninova V, Nikitina I, Malyavskaya S, Dolbnya S, et al. Vitamin D insufficiency in overweight and obese children and adolescents. *Frontiers in endocrinology*. 2019;10:103.
- Abramczyk U, Kuzan A. What Every Diabetologist Should Know about SARS-CoV-2: State of Knowledge at the Beginning of 2021. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2021;10(5):1022.
- Ogden CL, Carroll MD, Fryar CD, Flegal KM. Prevalence of obesity among adults and youth: United States, 2011-2014. 2015.
- Organization WH. Obesity: preventing and managing the global epidemic. Report of a World Health Organization Consultation. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2000. WHO Obesity Technical Report Series, 2017.
- Patnaik L, Pattanaik S, Sahu T, Rao EV. Overweight and obesity among adolescents–A comparative study between government and private schools. *Indian pediatrics*. 2015;52(9):779-81.
- Mansur D, Haque M, Sharma K, Mehta D, Shakya R. A study on nutritional status of rural school going children in Kavre District. *Kathmandu University Medical Journal*. 2015;13(2):146-51.
- Caleyachetty R, Thomas G, Kengne AP, Echouffo-Tcheugui JB, Schilsky S, Khodabocus J, et al. The double burden of malnutrition among adolescents: analysis of data from the Global School-Based Student Health and Health Behavior in School-Aged Children surveys in 57 low-and middle-income countries. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*. 2018;108(2):414-24.
- Winck AD, Heinzmann-Filho JP, Soares RB, Silva JSd, Woszezenki CT, Zanatta LB. Effects of obesity on lung volume and capacity in children and adolescents: a systematic review. *Revista Paulista de Pediatria*. 2016;34:510
- Marques A, Peralta M, Naia A, Loureiro N, de Matos MG. Prevalence of adult overweight and obesity in 20 European countries, 2014. *The European Journal of Public Health*. 2018;28(2):295-300.
- Ortega FB, Lavie CJ, Blair SN. Obesity and cardiovascular disease. *Circulation research*. 2016;118(11):1752-70.

- Teferi DY, Atomssa GE, Mekonnen TC. Overweight and undernutrition in the cases of school-going adolescents in Wolaita Sodo town, southern Ethiopia: cross-sectional study. *Journal of nutrition and metabolism*. 2018;2018.
- Yetubie M, Haidar J, Kassa H, Fallon F. Socioeconomic and demographic factors affecting body mass index of adolescents students aged 10–19 in Ambo (a rural town) in Ethiopia. *International journal of biomedical science: IJBS*. 2010;6(4):321.
- Anteneh ZA, Gedefaw M, Tekletsadek KN, Tsegaye M, Alemu D. Risk factors of overweight and obesity among high school students in Bahir Dar city, North West Ethiopia: school based cross-sectional study. *Advances in Preventive Medicine*. 2015;2015.
- Manyanga T, El-Sayed H, Doku DT, Randall JR. The prevalence of underweight, overweight, obesity and associated risk factors among school-going adolescents in seven African countries. *BMC public health*. 2014;14(1):1-11.
- Gebreyohannes Y, Shiferaw S, Demtsu B, Bugssa G. Nutritional status of adolescents in selected government and private secondary schools of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *Adolescence*. 2014;10(11).
- Jagadesan S, Harish R, Miranda P, Unnikrishnan R, Anjana RM, Mohan V. Prevalence of overweight and obesity among school children and adolescents in Chennai. *Indian pediatrics*. 2014;51(7):544-9.
- Damie T, Wondafrash M, Teklehaymanot A. Nutritional status and associated factors among school adolescent in Chiro Town, West Hararge, Ethiopia. *Gaziantep Medical Journal*. 2015;21(1):32-42.

Author Information

Dr Zarnab Munir

post graduate trainee Medicine SKBZH/CMH
Muzaffarabad AJK

Dr Munazza Nazir

Assot Prof Medicine AJKMC,SKBZH/CMH
Muzaffarabd, AJK

Dr Mudasar Hafiz

post graduate trainee Medicine SKBZH/CMH
Muzaffarab AJK

Dr Rubina Rafique

Assit Prof Medicine AJKMC,AIMS Muzaffarbad
AJK

Dr Nouman Kareem Qurashi

Assit Prof Gastroenterology AJKMC,SKBZH/CMH
Muzaffarabd AJK

Dr Naheem Ahmed

Assot prof peads AJKMC, SKBH/CMH
Muzaffarabad AJK
